

D7.2

Geospatial open data repository

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Deliverable 7.2 Geospatial open data repository

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Datasets associated with the deliverable

Geospatial open data repository for soil biodiversity and soil health data (D7.2) -

<https://zenodo.org/records/15798496>

Table of Contents

Document Information.....	2
Table of Contents	3
Executive Summary	4

Executive Summary

The deliverable D7.2 “Geospatial open data repository for soil biodiversity and soil health data” consists of a database deposited in an open access repository ([ZENODO](#)) which includes data obtained from the analysis of different parameters related to soil biodiversity and soil health of the farms included in the [Soil O-live project](#).

The parameters included in this database are the plant diversity of the cover crop, the ants and nematodes (free-living and plant parasitic) diversity in the soil, as well as data corresponding to soil metagenomic studies (bacteria and fungi). Finally, a soil health index was calculated for each one of the farms of the project. This index is built from eight soil indicators, including abiotic and biotic factors: soil organic carbon content, bulk density, NPK content, nitrification rates, soil respiration, electrical conductivity, richness of bacteria, fungi, and mycorrhizal and abundance of plant-parasitic nematodes.

Note: the database associated to this deliverable will have restricted access until the data included are successfully published. However, to obtain access you can contact the representative persons of the [ZENODO community](#) of the Soil O-live project.